

1 The Rising Misuse of Pharmacovigilance Reporting Systems: A Threat
2 to Evidence-Based Medicine

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4 Running heading: Misuse of Pharmacovigilance Reporting Systems

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34 **Abstract**

35 In recent years, different national and international regulatory authorities, notably the FDA,
36 have made their adverse event repositories publicly available, offering user-friendly
37 dashboards. This has led to a deluge of low-quality, misinterpreted research using adverse
38 event reporting databases (e.g., FDA's Adverse Event Reporting System - FAERS). Such
39 publications producing thousands of statistical associations presented as "safety signals" can
40 create unscientifically grounded alarm with considerable impact on healthcare provider
41 practices and patient behaviors.

42 As specialists in pharmacovigilance, we are committed to increasing the value of the
43 research conducted in the field. We believe the moment is crucial to share our concern and
44 prevent the scientific literature from being flooded with weak, catastrophist studies that
45 could harm patients and science itself. In this article, we perform a bibliometric analysis
46 showing the exponential rise in scientific publications in the field of pharmacovigilance, we
47 describe spontaneous reporting systems and signal detection analyses, their bias and
48 suited interpretation. Moreover, amid the recent rise in publications of pharmacovigilance
49 studies, notably those on FAERS, numerous articles display features that make them hard to
50 distinguish from those known to be that of 'paper mill' articles. Then we discuss the pros and
51 cons of publishing these studies, advocate for global collaborative efforts to reshape,
52 promote and increase best practices for conducting pharmacovigilance research. Lastly,
53 we propose criteria to identify high quality studies and robust safety signals coming from
54 adverse event reporting database, thus assisting stakeholders, including reviewers, editors,
55 regulators and researchers in critical appraisal of relevant findings.

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57 Adverse drug reactions are an important cause of hospital admission and lead to
58 significant burden on healthcare systems. It is estimated that they are responsible for an
59 average of 15.4% of hospital admissions (1), and that around half of them are considered
60 preventable (2). Timely identification of new safety issues and monitoring suspected adverse
61 effects of medicinal products is therefore a major public health challenge and studies on drug-
62 related risks often attract considerable media and public interest. Examples include myocardial
63 infarction or stroke with rofecoxib, venous thromboembolic events with oral contraceptives
64 and, more recently, myocarditis with Covid-19 vaccination. Although conventionally placed at
65 the bottom of the evidence-based medicine hierarchy, spontaneous reporting of suspected
66 adverse effects and published case reports still represent the most commonly used data
67 leading to the withdrawal, revocation or suspension of marketing authorizations of medicinal
68 products. In fact, case reports were recently estimated as supporting 94.4% of all regulatory
69 actions in EU (3). To achieve this, reports of suspected adverse drug reactions, termed
70 individual case safety reports (ICSRs), are routinely collected, assessed and stored in
71 dedicated databases by both regulators and marketing authorization holders. These
72 databases are then exploited by multiple stakeholders, including pharmaceutical companies,
73 regulatory agencies and researchers, to highlight associations between the reporting of
74 products and of events (using the so-called “disproportionality analyses” or “case-non case
75 approach”), and to identify index cases with intrinsic evidence strongly supporting a causal
76 relation.

77 **1. A deluge of low-quality publications**

78 In recent years, different national and international regulatory authorities have made
79 their adverse event repositories publicly available, offering user-friendly dashboards (4). While
80 this transparency is commendable, we are deeply concerned with the use of open online tools
81 by users without consolidated knowledge in pharmacovigilance and the related exponential
82 increase in scientific publications (**Figure 1**). This is especially true regarding the repository
83 managed by the Food and Drug Administration, called FAERS, which can be easily queried
84 via open online tools by users without consolidated expertise in the conduct, reporting and
85 interpretation of pharmacovigilance analyses based on ICSRs (5). This US data source was
86 the first to be made publicly available in this way. By presenting mere statistical associations
87 as “safety signals”, these publications can generate unjustified alarms with considerable
88 impact on healthcare provider practices and patient behaviors. Even more concerning are the
89 common (poor quality) features most of these studies present, i.e. they generally contain no
90 rationale, blindly apply generic methods, and provide results interpretation in an unspecific
91 standardized format overlooking inherent and study-specific pitfalls. Ultimately, they often

92 present results that would not withstand the scrutiny of experts in drug safety and medicine -
93 for example presenting the drug indications as unrecognized safety concerns.

94

95 **2. (Mis)interpretation of pharmacovigilance studies**

96 The study of adverse event reports is generally used among the first steps in the
97 identification and characterization of potential safety issues. Importantly, the inherent
98 limitations of adverse event reporting systems and the assumptions underlying
99 disproportionality analyses do not allow them to go beyond identifying 'leads'; and not to
100 definitively assess causal associations between a drug and an event (**Box 1**). However, a
101 meta-research study estimated that over two-thirds of published studies misinterpreted,
102 intentionally or not, their findings (i.e. the so-called "spin", often to enhance sensationalism
103 and newsworthiness and thus accessing higher ranking journals), in the form of: a) claiming
104 for causality without addressing potential biases, b) calculating/estimating incidence, and
105 c) providing unjustified clinical recommendations (6).

106 These published studies can then be quoted by other researchers, picked up by the
107 media, shared in social networks and may finally influence behaviors of healthcare
108 professionals and patients. A study highlighted, for example, that intense mediatic coverage
109 over the risks of statins was followed by a rise in unjustified statins discontinuation (7). During
110 the COVID pandemic, the French health minister's tweeted that people with suspected
111 COVID-19 should avoid anti-inflammatory drugs based on few observations of disease-
112 worsening after taking ibuprofen (8). This signal was never confirmed in subsequent
113 observational studies comparing users and non-users of NSAIDs on outcomes of patients with
114 COVID-19 (9). Yet this tweet was widely spread and lead to a huge drop in the use of ibuprofen
115 in France (8).

116

Box 1. Basic concept of pharmacovigilance studies

The growing availability of large-scale pharmacovigilance databases capturing millions of individual case safety reports (ICSRs) prompted researchers and regulators to develop automated computer-assisted procedures to prioritize ICSRs for medical review. This approach, popularly termed "data mining", starts with ICSRs management (removal of duplicates, data standardization, transformation and codification) and culminates with the application of statistical techniques. The initial step of ICSR processing is essential especially when approaching repositories with public unrestricted access to raw data, such as the FDA database (FAERS).

In early 1990s, the disproportionality concept was introduced and used at scale, and the "case/non-case" term was coined to better reflect the difference with the case-control design in pharmacoepidemiology. Disproportionality analysis is a statistical method based on aggregate analysis of ICSRs, looking for a potential association between pharmaceutical products and adverse events. Because ICSRs databases lack denominators (exposure-person time or true numbers of treatment-emergent adverse events), the basic idea in these is to compare, for a drug versus all

others, the proportion of reporting a given event represent (cases) with the proportion of reporting all other events represent (non-cases). When the imbalance between cases and non-cases exceeds a pre-specified threshold, a statistically significant disproportionality emerges, which is technically termed “signal of disproportionate reporting”.

Although several disproportionality metrics have been validated, no gold standard exists, and there is vehement debate on the reliability, accuracy and validity of disproportionality analysis, especially with respect to the ability for adequate control of confounding and biases (missing values, unavailable medical history, unpredictable influence of selective reporting). Due to these inherent limitations, and considering that disproportionality measures are inter-dependent, causality cannot be verified based solely on these data: a statistically significant disproportionality warrants integration with clinical (medical evaluation of individual ICSRs) and pharmacological (mechanistic plausibility) evaluation, it should be ideally validated by pharmacoepidemiologic research, and appraised in conjunction with other types of evidence (i.e. pharmacometrics, preclinical studies...) to assess the existence of a true adverse effect.

Nonetheless, within the science of pharmacovigilance disproportionality analysis is a powerful irreplaceable hypothesis-generating tool to timely uncover and characterize serious suspected adverse drug reactions with low background rate that cannot be fully appreciated during clinical trials or detected via healthcare databases.

Suggested readings

Bate A, Evans SJ. Quantitative signal detection using spontaneous ADR reporting. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.* 2009 Jun;18(6):427-36.

ENCePP. Chapter 11: Signal detection methodology and application (https://encepp.europa.eu/encepp-toolkit/methodological-guide/chapter-11-signal-detection-methodology-and-application_en).

European Medicines Agency. Guideline on good pharmacovigilance practices (GVP). Module IX Addendum I – Methodological aspects of signal detection from spontaneous reports of suspected adverse reactions (https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/guideline-good-pharmacovigilance-practices-gvp-module-ix-addendum-i-methodological-aspects-signal-detection-spontaneous-reports-suspected-adverse-reactions_en.pdf).

Report of CIOMS Working Group VIII - Practical Aspects of Signal Detection in Pharmacovigilance (<https://cioms.ch/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/WG8-Signal-Detection.pdf>).

117

118 **3. The unexpected consequences of openly accessible data**

119 Making data openly available is a laudable effort of regulatory agencies to increase
120 the transparency of safety data contained in adverse event reporting systems. The enormity
121 of adverse event reporting databases (e.g., as of April 2025, ≈ 40million reports in the WHO
122 database ‘VigiBase’ version for analysis and ≈ 30millionn in the FAERS public dashboard),
123 resulting in almost 5mln reported medicinal products-event pairs, combined with the many
124 possible analytical strategies with no gold-standard, makes these data an almost
125 inexhaustible source of statistical associations (10), thus, introducing a real risk of “cherry
126 picking” of significant results and data dredging (i.e., p-hacking). Hundreds of associations
127 are often tested by researchers, and dozens of statistical associations are frequently
128 presented in publications and erroneously described as safety signals, without any

129 adjustment for the multiplicity of tests carried out. Moreover, these databases are only
130 partially openly accessible, as case narratives are not routinely available and these often
131 contain clinically insightful information for assessing plausibility, therefore hampering the
132 effective contextualization of the statistical analyses with causality assessment at the case
133 level.

134 This could raise the question of whether these studies, which present a questionable
135 benefit-risk ratio for both knowledge and patient treatment, deserve to be published, given
136 the risk of harm they represent (“first do no harm”).

137

138 **4. Publish or not publish disproportionality analyses**

139 For the reasons presented above, whether analyses of adverse event reports should
140 be published or not in the scientific literature remains a contentious issue, with both valid
141 and flawed arguments on both sides.

142 Scientific knowledge is inherently provisional, as Austin Bradford Hill said “All
143 scientific work is liable to be upset or modified by advancing knowledge. That does not
144 confer upon us a freedom to ignore the knowledge we already have, or to postpone the
145 action that it appears to demand at a given time”. This principle is especially relevant in
146 pharmacovigilance, where case reports—whether from the literature or pharmacovigilance
147 reporting systems—have sometimes provided at a specific time the only available evidence
148 of a potential drug-related risk (11). This is particularly critical for newly marketed medicinal
149 products or adverse effects more easily recognizable from the patient’s perspective.

150 Nonetheless, there are legitimate concerns about the impact on public health of
151 publishing disproportionality analyses of adverse event reports. As discussed above,
152 misuse and misinterpretation of these analyses have increasingly led to unjustified safety
153 alerts, creating ungrounded regulatory or clinical concern. Even when properly
154 documented, any study has the potential to trigger unwarranted alarm, particularly among
155 readers without expertise in pharmacovigilance. Patients, general practitioners,
156 researchers outside the field will consume uncritically the studies about disproportionality
157 analysis and exaggerate their outcomes (12). Additionally, over-reliance on
158 disproportionality as a stand-alone tool risk obscuring genuine safety signals by reinforcing
159 statistical artifacts rather than prioritizing clinically relevant findings.

160 At the same time, there are compelling reasons to publish disproportionality findings,
161 particularly their role in hypothesis generation (including the underlying mechanistic basis),
162 prioritization, and preliminary validation. Publication promotes transparency, supports
163 evidence synthesis, and ensures that safety concerns emerging from adverse event reports
164 are not confined to forgotten grey literature. However, poor motivations for publication also
165 exist and may dominate in the current academic climate. Pressures related to career

166 incentives and the "publish or perish" culture encourage the dissemination of huge amounts
167 of low-quality, decontextualized findings. Given the aforementioned ease of generating
168 disproportionality results, the high chance of false positive results is often overlooked, either
169 due to personal interests or cognitive biases such as the excitement of perceiving patterns
170 in noise (13).

171 There are three possible approaches to the use and dissemination of
172 disproportionality analyses. The first is to retain results as an internal pharmacovigilance
173 tool for signal detection and prioritization, without direct publication with the challenge of
174 limiting transparency and learnings for other researchers. Regulators routinely posted key
175 results of their signal detection activity, although relevant characterization and
176 corroboration is often neglected by researchers (14). The second, fundamentally flawed, is
177 to (continue) publish disproportionality findings in isolation as conclusive evidence. The
178 third, requiring significantly more methodological rigour and effort, is to integrate
179 disproportionality findings within a broader evidence framework. This approach explicitly
180 acknowledges biases, clarifies methodological assumptions, and carefully distinguishes
181 between observed reporting associations (what is found) and recognised adverse drug
182 reactions (what is sought) through appropriate causal and associational language.
183 Moreover, it positions disproportionality analysis as just one piece of the evidence puzzle,
184 complementing case-by-case and case series assessments (intrinsic evidence) and the
185 synthesis of other pre-clinical, pharmacological and clinical sources evidence.

186

Box 2. What defines a robust disproportionality study and safety signal deserving consideration?

- Methodological quality
 - Protocol pre-registration or predefined transparent process for routine use of disproportionality
 - Transparency of methods (reproducibility)
 - No assumptions of disproportionality analysis strongly violated
 - Consistent sensitivity analyses / stability to stress-tests on expected biases
 - Adequate / cautious choice of the reporting period to be studied
- Intrinsic evidence of causality (the need of defining and identifying index cases)*
 - Certainty of diagnosis (i.e., disease adequately diagnosed by specific exams)
 - Lack of obvious alternative causes (e.g., viral infections in drug-induced liver injury)
 - Plausible temporal association with what is known about the disease and the pharmacology of the medicinal product
 - Improvement after drug withdrawal (dechallenge) and relapse of the disease after reintroduction of the drug (rechallenge)
 - Common pattern among cases (similarity of onset delay, patients with common characteristics, etc.)
- Concordant evidence from very different studies (triangulation of evidence)

- Supportive experimental evidence (e.g., in vitro, in vivo, ex vivo mechanistic data)
- Synthetic data (e.g., in silico approaches and “omics” computational analysis)
- Observational data (e.g., electronic medical records, registries or claims databases)

** the importance of the criteria will vary greatly by nature of drug and AE for more details see for example Edwards, I.R. and Aronson, J.K., 2000. Adverse drug reactions: definitions, diagnosis, and management. The lancet, 356(9237), pp.1255-1259.*

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188 **5. Features of recently published disproportionality analyses**

189 Amid the recent rise in publications of pharmacovigilance studies, notably those on
190 FAERS, numerous articles display features that make them hard to distinguish from those
191 known to be that of ‘paper mill’ articles (i.e., for-profit organizations that systematically produce
192 and sell papers to authors). Numerous articles using similar formatting and style (same figures,
193 methods and tables), and containing obvious errors in technical terms translation. For
194 example, methods of disproportionality analyses such as “Bayesian confidence propagation
195 neural network” are frequently reported as “Bayesian confidence interval progressive neural
196 network”, “Bayesian belief propagation neural network”, or “Bayesian configuration promotion
197 neural network”. While clearly all refer to the same specific method. Such patterns and errors
198 of course may just be an artifact of democratization of access to safety data and/or wider use,
199 and whether these features only indicate poor quality research or the involvement of paper
200 mills remains to be further investigated.

201

202 **6. Recommendations for trustworthy pharmacovigilance**

203

204 Transparency, robustness, accuracy, validity and reproducibility of disproportionality
205 analyses are current mantras of modern pharmacovigilance and we advocate for global
206 collaborative efforts to reshape, promote and increase best practices for conducting
207 pharmacovigilance research. We started few years ago by developing the first
208 recommendations for reporting studies based on suspected adverse effect reporting
209 systems (15). We are now collectively working on the development of a specific risk of bias
210 tool, and we tried to express in the **Box 2** our vision on whether pharmacovigilance results
211 from adverse event reporting systems are valid, robust and convincing to deserve further
212 consideration. These *minimum requirements* may assist stakeholders, reviewers, editors,
213 regulators and researchers in critical appraisal of relevant findings. Hopefully, these criteria
214 will support the responsible use and publication of disproportionality analyses, thus finally
215 reaffirming their value within the evidence landscape for evidence-based decision making.

216

217 In this era of misinformation and disinformation and its impact on public health,
systematic research is needed on how apparent emerging safety issues are communicated

218 in the literature and the impact that they have on public health including the extent to which
219 poor quality erroneous issues impact patient safety.
220

KEY POINTS

- A deluge of low-quality, misinterpreted research using adverse event reporting databases (e.g., FDA's Adverse Event Reporting System - FAERS) has been recently published.
- These publications can generate unjustified alarms with considerable impact on healthcare provider practices and patient behaviors.
- We advocate for global collaborative efforts to reshape, promote and increase best practices for conducting pharmacovigilance research on adverse event reporting databases.
- We propose criteria to identify high quality studies and robust safety signals coming from adverse event reporting database, thus assisting stakeholders, including reviewers, editors, regulators and researchers in critical appraisal of relevant findings

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273 **Figure**
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277 **Figure 1.** Bibliometric analysis on published pharmacovigilance studies in PubMed*. FAERS:
278 FDA Adverse Event Reporting System; JADER: Japanese Adverse Event Reporting System;
279 VAERS: Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System.

280 * PubMed research query (March 1, 2025): ("case/non-case" OR "case-non-case" OR "case/no-case" OR "Disproportionality"
281 OR "Information Component" OR "Reporting Odds Ratio" OR "Proportional Reporting Ratio" OR "multi-item gamma Poisson
282 shrinker") AND
283 ("FAERS" OR "Vigibase" OR "Eudravigilance" OR "VAERS" OR "JADER" OR "pharmacovigilance Database" OR "Reporting
284 system" OR "Adverse Event Reporting System" OR "Yellow card" OR "FEDRA" OR "BNPV")

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286

287 **Authors contributions**

288 As specialists in real-world evidence and drug safety, and more specifically in
289 pharmacovigilance, we are committed to increasing the value of the research conducted in
290 the field. As such, MF, FS, ER and CK steered the elaboration of the first guideline for the
291 reporting of Pharmacovigilance studies (READUS-PV). This was done before 2024 during
292 which the number of publications in the field from open databases literally exploded. AP,
293 AB, ER, CK and FS started to share their concerns by exchanging messages abouts the
294 poor quality of some publications and decided to invite other co-authors with different
295 locations and perspectives (NJ as editor in chief of the leading journal in pharmacovigilance,
296 MF from the Uppsala Monitoring Center) to wrote this article to raise awareness among
297 health professionals, researchers, journal editors and regulators. AH performed the
298 bibliometric analysis, and CK wrote the first draft. All other authors contributed to revising
299 it critically and agreed on the final content. CK is the guarantor.

300

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304

305 **Conflicts of Interest**

306 All opinions expressed in this commentary represent the views of the authors and do not
307 represent the views of any listed employer or institution. We have not been paid to write this
308 article and have no conflict of interest related to this study. One of us (AB) is an employee
309 of a pharmaceutical company, his role is as like the rest of us an expert in the analysis of
310 spontaneous reports and he is widely cited having for example been first author of one of the
311 earlier publications (Bate et al, Eur J Clin Pharmacol 1998). He reports no conflict of interest
312 with this specific study.

313

314 **Data availability**

315 The data used for the bibliometric analysis are openly accessible on Pubmed.

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317